

**INVESTIGATION OF TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY BELIEFS ACCORDING TO
VARIOUS VARIABLES**

**ÖĞRETMENLERİN ÖZ YETERLİK İNANÇLARININ ÇEŞİTLİ DEĞİŞKENLERE GÖRE
İNCELENMESİ**

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ABSTRACT

The aim of the study was to determine the differentiation of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to various variables in different school types. In line with the determined purpose, scanning model was preferred as the method in the research. The population of the research consists of teachers in schools affiliated with basic education working in different branches and school types in the 2023-2024 academic year. The sample of the research consists of 439 teachers randomly selected from among the teachers working in these schools. In the study, "Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale" was used as a data collection tool to reveal teachers' self-efficacy beliefs. The scale is the Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale Short Form developed by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001), adapted into Turkish by Erdoğan (2023). In the study, it was determined that a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender variable was in favor of male teachers. It was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to the variables of branch, professional seniority and type of school where they work. According to the results, it can be evaluated that the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers participating in the research are not similar to the demographic variables of the research: gender, branch, professional seniority and type of school where they work.

Keywords: Teacher, Self-Efficacy, Self-Efficacy Belief.

ÖZET

Araştırmada farklı okul türlerinde göre yapan öğretmenlerin öz yeterlik inançlarının çeşitli değişkenlere göre farklılaşma durumunun belirlenmesi amaçlanmıştır. Belirlenen amaç doğrultusunda araştırmada yöntem olarak tarama modeli tercih edilmiştir. Araştırmanın evrenini 2023-2024 eğitim-öğretim yılında farklı branş ve okul türlerinde görev yapan temel eğitime bağlı okullardaki öğretmenler oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmanın örneklemini ise bu okullarda görev yapan öğretmenler arasından seçkisiz olarak belirlenen 439 öğretmen oluşturmaktadır. Araştırmada öğretmenlerin öz yeterlik inançlarını ortaya koymak amacıyla "Öğretmen Öz yeterlik Ölçeği" veri toplama aracı olarak kullanılmıştır. Ölçek Tschannen-Moran ve Woolfolk Hoy (2001) tarafından geliştirilen Öğretmen Öz Yeterliği Ölçeği Kısa Formu'nu ölçek Erdoğan (2023) tarafından Türkçeye uyarlanmış şeklidir. Araştırmada öğretmenlerin öz yeterlik inançları arasında cinsiyet

değişkenine göre anlamlı bir farklılığın erkek öğretmenler lehine olduğu belirlenmiştir. Branş, mesleki kıdem ve görev yapılan okul türü değişkenlerine göre de öğretmenlerin öz yeterlik inançları arasında anlamlı bir farklılığın olduğu belirlenmiştir. Ulaşılan sonuçlara göre araştırmaya katılan öğretmenlerin öz yeterlik inançlarının araştırmanın demografik değişkenleri olan cinsiyet, branş, mesleki kıdem ve görev yapılan okul türü değişkenlerine göre benzerlik göstermediği şeklinde değerlendirilebilir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Öğretmen, Öz Yeterlik, Öz Yeterlik İnancı

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is the most important factor in raising future generations. A qualified education and teacher have a great role in order for societies to raise individuals with the desired qualifications. In order for teachers, who are an indispensable element of the education system, to perform their profession correctly, they must receive a qualified education and be equipped with professional knowledge, skills and competencies during the pre-service training process. Competence, which is one of the important qualities to perform the teaching task, is basically acquired during the teacher education process and develops in the process after starting the profession (Baloğlu and Karadağ, 2008). The basic competencies of the teaching profession consist of three main eleven sub-competencies and sixty-five directives: professional knowledge and skills, attitudes and values (MEB, 2017).

A teacher who has acquired the basic competencies of the profession must believe that he can carry out learning and teaching activities. This belief is explained by the concept of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is defined as the individual's personal belief that they can produce something in line with their wishes (Maddux, 2000) and that they will be successful in coping with the difficult situations they will encounter in their future lives (Senemoğlu, 2007). Individuals with self-efficacy beliefs also have the tendency to resist difficulties, strive for their work, and set difficult goals for themselves (Schunk and Usher, 2012). Self-efficacy belief is based on the individual's judgment of what he can do with his knowledge and skills, not on his skills and abilities (Bong and Skaalvik, 2003).

Although various types of self-efficacy are defined in the literature, one of them was made by Tschannen-Moran, Woolfolk-Hoy and Hoy (1998). The authors defined teacher self-efficacy belief as "the belief in one's own competence in organizing and carrying out the actions necessary for the successful performance of a specific teaching task in a specific context." It has been stated that teachers' beliefs about their own competencies are a factor that affects their judgments and perceptions and their attitudes in the classroom environment (Pajares, 1992).

Self-efficacy is an important concept that should be taken into account when explaining teacher behaviors. Teacher self-efficacy, which plays a critical role in students' motivation to help them learn, was examined by Melby (1995; cited in Bandura, 1997) and found that teachers with low self-efficacy had difficulties in classroom management, were dissatisfied with the teaching profession, and became more stressed in the face of undesirable student behavior. It has been revealed that they do not focus on the development of the student by communicating the teaching issue directly to the student, but are pessimistic and would not choose the teaching profession again if given the opportunity.

It has been stated that when teacher self-efficacy belief (Ross, 1992), which is effective in the formation of desired student outcomes, is low, teachers' professional stress levels are high, their job satisfaction is low and they experience more difficulties in the teaching process (Betoret, 2006). Teachers with low self-efficacy beliefs, which are effective in their motivation and success, will find it difficult to motivate them unless they believe in their abilities, and when faced with a

challenge, they will give up more quickly than teachers with high self-efficacy beliefs (Gurvitch & Metzler, 2009). The criteria created by the teacher or teacher candidate on how to teach well also have an impact on self-efficacy belief (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2007).

When the relevant literature is examined, self-efficacy, which is a concept mostly studied in the field of education, can be expressed as "self-efficacy", "self-efficacy perception", "self-efficacy belief", "self-efficacy expectation" in Turkish. The concept of self-efficacy, which was first used by Bandura in 1977 within the framework of "Cognitive Behavioral Change", is defined as "the person's belief in his ability to organize and succeed in the activities required to achieve a performance" (Bandura, 1997). Although having different skills is not the same as demonstrating these skills when necessary, lack of belief in displaying the knowledge and skills when necessary will affect functionality (Bandura, 1997).

Aşkar and Umay (2001) stated that people with high self-efficacy do not give up easily in the face of difficulties, are patient and resilient, and strive to be successful in a certain job. Self-efficacy is defined as the individual's personal belief that they can produce something in line with their wishes (Maddux, 2000) and that they will be successful in coping with the difficult situations they will encounter in their future lives (Senemoğlu, 2007). In the context of education, teacher self-efficacy is defined as teachers' beliefs and perceptions in their ability to achieve the desired results from students' learning during the teaching process (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001; Geijssel, Slegers, Stoel, & Krüger, 2009).

Teacher self-efficacy, which expresses the confidence that one can overcome the obstacles encountered in the educational process involving teaching and learning, is expressed as the teacher's belief in their ability to plan, organize, carry out teaching activities and fulfill the determined goals of education. Teachers with high self-efficacy are reported to have higher commitment to the profession (Coladarci, 1992), are less likely to leave the profession (Burley, Hall, Villeme, & Brockmeier, 1991), have lower levels of burnout (Skaalvik & Skaalvik, 2010), and have lower academic performance. It is claimed that they insist on patient solutions to the difficulties that arise while executing the work.

1.1. Purpose of the research

In this research, it was aimed to determine the differentiation of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to various variables in different school types. In this context, answers were sought to the following questions:

1. What is the level of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs?
2. Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender variable?
3. Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to the branch variable?
4. Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to the professional seniority variable?
5. Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs depending on the type of school they work in?

2. METHOD

2.1. Model of the Research

The survey model was used as a method in this research, which aims to determine the differentiation of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to various variables in different school types.

2.2. Population and Sample of the Research

The population of the research consists of teachers in schools affiliated with basic education working in different branches and school types in the 2023-2024 academic year. The sample of the research consists of 439 teachers randomly selected from among the teachers working in these schools. 59.5% of the participating teachers were women, 40.5% were men, 20.7% worked in pre-schools, 27.3% worked in primary schools, 51.9% worked in secondary schools, and 18.9% worked in secondary schools. u 1-5, 20.5% 6-10, 27.8% 11-15, 19.1% 16-20 and 13.7% 21 and above. Additionally, 23.5% of the teachers taught Classroom, 20.7% taught Preschool, 9.8% taught English, 7.7% taught Turkish, 7.5% taught Social Studies, 7.3% taught English. Science, 12.3% are from Primary Mathematics, and 11.2% are from other branches.

2.3. Data Collection and Data Collection Tools

"Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale" was used to reveal teachers' self-efficacy beliefs. The Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale Short Form developed by Tschannen-Moran and Woolfolk Hoy (2001) was adapted into Turkish by Erdoğan (2023). While it was determined that the Cronbach's alpha (α) coefficients calculated during the adaptation process of the scale varied between ".78" and ".93", the research found that this range varied between ".82" and ".91".

2.4. Analysis of Data

In order to reveal teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the study, parametric inferential statistical methods were used in addition to descriptive statistical methods, since the data collected with the "Teacher Self-Efficacy Scale" exhibited normal distribution (± 1.00 Kurtosis-Skewness). Independent Groups t test and One-Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) were used as inferential statistical methods. SPSS 25.0 package program was used to analyze the data.

3. FINDING

3.1. Findings on Teachers' Self-Efficacy Beliefs

The study's question: "What is the level of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs?" Descriptive statistical analysis data calculated within the framework of the sub-problem are presented in Table 1.

Tablo 1. Analysis data of teachers' self-efficacy belief level

Dimensions	Mean	SS
Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management	6,25	1,101
Self-Efficacy for Student Participation	6,57	1,156
Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies	6,61	1,239
General	6,47	1,055

In Table 1, the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs is "6.47" and the self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension is "6.25"; "6.57" in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension; It is understood that it is "6.61" in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension. It can be said that teachers' self-efficacy belief averages are close to each other on the basis of dimensions.

3.2. Findings Regarding the Gender Variable

The study's question: "Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender variable?" The analysis data performed within the framework of the sub-problem is presented in Table 2.

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Table 2. Analysis data by gender

Dimensions	Gender	n	Mean	SS	t	p
Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management	Female	261	5,85	,995	-1,790	,00*
	Male	178	6,83	,982		
Self-Efficacy for Student Participation	Female	261	6,26	1,075	1,064	,00*
	Male	178	7,02	1,122		
Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies	Female	261	6,27	1,156	1,061	,00*
	Male	178	7,11	1,186		
General	Female	261	6,12	,978	,101	,00*
	Male	178	6,99	,952		

*p<0,05

When Table 2 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference according to gender in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). The significant difference

determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension is seen to be in favor of male teachers as a result of the examination of the averages.

When Table 2 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference according to gender in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). The significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension is seen to be in favor of male teachers as a result of the examination of the averages.

When Table 2 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference according to gender in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). The significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension is seen to be in favor of male teachers as a result of the examination of the averages.

When Table 2 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender, according to the analysis results among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). The significant difference determined is seen to be in favor of male teachers as a result of examining the averages.

3.3. Findings Regarding the Branch Variable

The study's question: "Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to the branch variable?" The analysis data performed within the framework of the sub-problem is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Analysis data by branch

Dimensions	Branch	n	Mean	SS	F	p
Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management	1. Classroom teaching	103	6,57	1,038	13,451	,00*
	2. Pre-school	91	5,79	,679		1-6
	3.English	43	6,81	1,066		3-6
	4.Türkish	34	6,18	1,118		4-6
	5. Social studies	33	6,59	1,043		5-6
	6. science	32	5,09	1,635		7-6
	7. Primary Mathematics	54	6,54	,658		8-6
	8. Other	49	6,18	1,064		2-1
						2-3
						2-5
						2-7

Continued from Table 3

Dimensions	Branch	n	Mean	SS	F	p
Self-Efficacy for Student Participation	1. Classroom teaching	103	6,86	1,174	9,071	,00* 1-6 2-6 3-6 4-6 5-6 7-6 8-6
	2. Pre-school	91	6,44	,800		
	3.English	43	7,15	1,083		
	4.Türkish	34	6,40	1,295		
	5. Social studies	33	6,58	1,067		
	6. science	32	5,35	1,805		
	7. Primary Mathematics	54	6,71	,673		
	8. Other	49	6,43	,974		
Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies	1. Classroom teaching	103	6,89	1,341	8,024	,00* 1-6 2-6 3-6 4-6 5-6 7-6
	2. Pre-school	91	6,51	,865		
	3.English	43	7,26	1,428		
	4.Türkish	34	6,52	1,321		
	5. Social studies	33	6,62	1,049		
	6. science	32	5,42	1,715		
	7. Primary Mathematics	54	6,72	,756		
	8. Other	49	6,34	,954		
General	1. Classroom teaching	103	6,77	1,075	11,820	,00* 1-6 2-6 3-6 4-6 5-6 7-6 8-6 2-3
	2. Pre-school	91	6,25	,657		
	3.English	43	7,07	1,093		
	4.Türkish	34	6,37	1,145		
	5. Social studies	33	6,60	,933		
	6. science	32	5,28	1,679		
	7. Primary Mathematics	54	6,66	,435		
	8. Other	49	6,32	,837		

When Table 3 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research, depending on the branch in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of the multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined was between teachers with a Science branch and teachers with other branches. It was also determined that the significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was between teachers in the pre-school branch and teachers in the classroom-English-social-primary education mathematics branches.

When Table 3 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research according to the branch in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined is between teachers with Science branches and teachers with other branches.

When Table 3 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research according to the branch in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of the multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined was between teachers with a Science branch and teachers with other branches.

When Table 3 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to the branch, according to the analysis results among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests, the determined significant difference is between teachers with Science branches and teachers with other branches. It was also determined that the significant difference was between teachers in the pre-school branch and teachers in the English branch.

3.4. Findings Regarding the Professional Seniority Variable

The question of the study was "Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to the professional seniority variable?" The analysis data made within the framework of the sub-problem are presented in Table 4.

Table 4 . Analysis data by professional seniority

Dimensions	Professional Seniority	n	Mean	SS	F	p	
Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management	1. 1-5	83	5,77	1,319	10,214	,00*	
	2. 6-10	90	5,95	1,050			1-3
	3. 11-15	122	6,59	,922			1-4
	4. 16-20	84	6,38	1,001			1-5
	5. 21 and +	60	6,47	,992			2-3

Self-Efficacy for Student Participation	1. 1-5	83	6,03	1,353	8,286	,00*
	2. 6-10	90	6,40	1,138		
	3. 11-15	122	6,87	1,026		
	4. 16-20	84	6,71	,985		
	5. 21 and +	60	6,75	1,090		
Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies	1. 1-5	83	6,03	1,482	8,529	,00*
	2. 6-10	90	6,41	1,129		
	3. 11-15	122	6,90	1,128		
	4. 16-20	84	6,85	1,124		
	5. 21 and +	60	6,79	1,093		
General	1. 1-5	83	5,94	1,301	10,946	,00*
	2. 6-10	90	6,25	,998		
	3. 11-15	122	6,79	,895		
	4. 16-20	84	6,65	,929		
	5. 21 and +	60	6,67	,891		

*p<0,05

When Table 4 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension according to professional seniority ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined is between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years of seniority or more. It was also determined that the significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was between teachers with 6-10 years of seniority and teachers with 11-15 years of seniority.

When Table 4 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension according to professional seniority ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years of seniority and above.

When Table 4 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension according to professional seniority ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension, the

significant difference determined was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years or more of seniority.

When Table 4 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to their professional seniority, according to the analysis results among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests, the significant difference determined was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years of seniority and above. It was also determined that the significant difference was between teachers with 6-10 years of seniority and teachers with 11-15 years of seniority.

3.5. Findings Regarding the School Type Variable

The question of the study is "Is there a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs depending on the type of school they work in?" The analysis data performed within the framework of the sub-problem is presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Analysis data according to the type of school served

Dimensions	School Type	n	Mean	SS	F	p
Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management	1. Pre-school	91	5,79	,679	24,118	,00*
	2. Primary school	120	6,77	,927		1-2
	3. Middle school	228	6,16	1,213		1-3 2-3
Self-Efficacy for Student Participation	1. Pre-school	91	6,44	,800	23,433	,00*
	2. Primary school	120	7,15	1,044		1-2
	3. Middle school	228	6,31	1,225		1-3
Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies	1. Pre-school	91	6,51	,865	24,195	,00*
	2. Primary school	120	7,23	1,104		1-2
	3. Middle school	228	6,32	1,315		1-3
General	1. Pre-school	91	6,25	,657	27,450	,00*
	2. Primary school	120	7,05	,889		1-2
	3. Middle school	228	6,26	1,150		1-3

* $p<0,05$

When Table 5 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension depending on the type of school they work in ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a

result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools. It was also determined that the significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was between teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

When Table 5 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension depending on the type of school they work in ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

When Table 5 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension depending on the type of school they work in ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension, the significant difference determined is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

When Table 5 is examined, it is understood that there is a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs among the self-efficacy beliefs of the teachers who participated in the research, depending on the type of school they work in ($p=.00$; $p<.05$). As a result of multiple comparison tests, the significant difference determined was between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

4. RESULTS

In the research, it was determined that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs were above average. It was determined that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs were highest in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension and lowest in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension. According to this finding, it can be said that their self-efficacy for teaching strategies is in a better state.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension. The significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was found to be in favor of male teachers when evaluated on the basis of the averages.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension. The significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension was found to be in favor of male teachers when evaluated on the basis of averages.

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In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to gender in terms of the general average of their self-efficacy beliefs. When evaluated on the basis of averages, the detected significant difference was found to be in favor of male teachers. Based on the significant difference results determined according to the

gender variable, it can be said that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs are not similar to each other. This result can be interpreted in another way as the fact that the averages are far from each other is effective in reaching this result.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension depending on the branch. It was determined that the significant difference detected was between teachers with Science branches and teachers with other branches in the sub-dimension of "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management". In addition, it was also determined that the significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was between teachers in the pre-school branch and teachers in the classroom-English-social-primary education mathematics branches.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension depending on the branch. The significant difference detected is between teachers with Science branches and teachers with other branches in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension depending on the branch. The significant difference detected is between teachers with Science branches and teachers with other branches in the sub-dimension of "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management".

According to the analysis results among teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs depending on the branch. The significant difference detected is between teachers with Science branches and teachers with other branches. In addition, it was also determined that the significant difference was between teachers in the pre-school branch and teachers in the English branch.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension according to professional seniority. As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension, the significant difference detected was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years or more of seniority. In addition, it was also determined that the significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was between teachers with 6-10 years of seniority and teachers with 11-15 years of seniority.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension according to professional seniority. As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension, the significant difference detected was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years or more of seniority.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension according to professional seniority. As a result of multiple comparison tests conducted in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension, the significant difference detected was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years or more of seniority.

According to the analysis results among teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs according to professional seniority. As a result of multiple comparison tests, the significant difference detected was between teachers with 1-5 years of seniority and teachers with 11 years or

more of seniority. In addition, it was also determined that the significant difference was between teachers with 6-10 years of seniority and teachers with 11-15 years of seniority.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension depending on the type of school they worked in. The significant difference detected is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools in the sub-dimension of "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management". In addition, it was also determined that the significant difference determined in the "Self-Efficacy for Classroom Management" sub-dimension was between teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation" sub-dimension depending on the type of school they worked in. The significant difference detected is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools in the sub-dimension of "Self-Efficacy for Student Participation".

In the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension depending on the type of school they worked in. The significant difference detected in the "Self-Efficacy for Teaching Strategies" sub-dimension is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

According to the analysis results among teachers' self-efficacy beliefs in the study, it was determined that there was a significant difference in the general average of teachers' self-efficacy beliefs depending on the type of school they worked in. The significant difference detected is between teachers working in pre-school education institutions and teachers working in primary and secondary schools.

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